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Relationship between social media marketing and young customers' purchase intention towards online shopping

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ABSTRACT

This study indicates the selected social media marketing (SMM) dimensions such as influence social media content, engagement and interaction, brand awareness and perception, and influencer marketing that have influence on young consumers and drive their online purchase decisions. This study addresses these factors focusing on the context of young consumers in Bangladesh. For this investigation, a quantitative approach is employed through a structured questionnaire survey, and the data was collected from 412 Bangladeshi young users age limit is between 18 to 30, who purchase their products in online platform. The young population is between the ages of 18 and 30, and these samples were selected purposively. Data was inputted through MS Excel, and the PLS-SEM version 4 software was used to evaluate the hypothesized relationships among the variables. The findings reveal that the influence of social media content, engagement and interaction, brand awareness and perception, and influencer marketing encourage the young customer in social interactions that significantly influence their purchase decisions. This research contributes to a deeper understanding of how this young generation interacts with SMM and how businesses can leverage these SMM dimensions (content, engagement, brand perception) to effectively reach and convert this important online shopping demographic in Bangladesh.

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1. Introduction

Nowadays, the social media environment is perceived by customers differently, particularly in the business area. The present era is characterized by a high level of internet usage, which provides a remarkable opportunity to engage with numerous individuals on a unified platform, without the need for physical interaction (Gruzd *et al.*, 2011). Consequently, social media plays a crucial role in the recent area of research due to digital technology. Various users can use the internet and share their content online and exchange different information with their friends and the public. According to Turban *et al.* (2009), 'Social media refer to the online platforms and tools that people use to share opinions and experiences including photos, videos, music, insights and perceptions with each other'. Similarly, Chanthinok *et al.* (2015) explained social media marketing as a strategic utilization of social media platforms to engage with current and new users, foster information and content sharing, and facilitate user interactions. The scholars additionally claimed social media marketing is an important factor nowadays because it allows firms to gauge the performance of their marketing strategies by tracking the number of hits they receive on various social media channels. Social media platforms also enable users to provide comments and information to the organization's staff, thereby facilitating the improvement of user services and resources.

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However, customer behavior is of another importance in all industries as businesses need to understand how customer desires and preferences are evolving in today's world. Changes in culture, economy and technology can significantly impact customer behavior leading to adjustments in studies, methods and objectives related to understanding this behavior. This study focuses particularly on the purchasing behavior of customers that refers to the steps they take when deciding whether to buy a product or service. It involves considering factors such as when, why, and how they make their purchase choices (Peighambari *et al.*, 2016). Additionally, companies can leverage social media platforms to control the information that they share with their target customers. Engaging with customers through dialogue on these platforms can enhance customer interaction. Businesses operating on media are becoming increasingly aware of its influence as it can impact customers' purchasing decisions. Thus, by utilizing social media presence companies can increase website traffic, revenue generation, customer satisfaction levels, trustworthiness perception, among clients and overall decision-making quality (Cabales *et al.*, 2023).

This review of existing literature leads to explore the relationship between social media marketing, recognizing its multifaceted nature and the necessity to examine different aspects within this field. Many researchers (for example, Nibir *et al.*, 2024; Singgalen, 2024; Owusu Yeboah *et al.*, 2024; Sandunima & Jayasuriya, 2024; Islam *et al.*, 2024; Garg & Kumar, 2021) have conducted studies on this relationship, which have enlarged our understanding of how social media affects our tendency to make online purchases. Many investigations have been conducted on this relationship from different perspective, for instance, Kula *et al.* (2021) investigated how media, online customer reviews, social influence, and website designs, and features impact purchase intention among consumers. Research conducted by Yu *et al.* (2022) addressed the relationship between buyer motivations and online buying intentions of fashion products in the context of social media marketing. Additionally, this study revealed that consumer commitment has a mediating effect on this relationship. On the other hand, Moslehpour *et al.* (2020) explored how social media marketing influences the purchasing intentions of consumers, in relation to airline products and services. According to Shwastika and Keni (2021), there is a significant connection between brand recognition, the perception of quality and promotional sales when it comes to influencing consumer purchasing decisions.

However, the impact of social media marketing and the desire for a shopping experience have influenced purchase intentions. Moreover, research shows that social media advertising plays a contributory role in affecting the consumer purchase intentions as it helps increase brand awareness, credibility, and ultimately influences their decisions to make a purchase (Khan & Bhutto, 2023). This study indicates that social media marketing (SMM) has revolutionized the way businesses connect with and influence consumers. In this sense, young consumers are a key demographic known for their active social media engagement. The above discussion anticipates the relationship between SMM and young consumers' purchase intention in the context of online shopping. By focusing on the dimensions of brand awareness and perception, engaging content marketing, and social interaction and engagement, this review aims to understand how SMM strategies influence young consumers' online purchase decisions. Based on the literature review support, this study explores the relationship between social media marketing (SMM) and young consumers' purchase intention in online shopping, focusing on four key dimensions: influence of social media content, engagement and interaction, brand awareness and perception, and influencer marketing impact.

However, the present study explained the relationship between SMM, and purchase intention based on the concept of the Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM) model. The ELM was first developed by Petty and Cacioppo (1986). Following this concept, we propose the present theoretical framework for comprehending the connection between SMM and the desire of young consumers. The contention of the ELM is that the degree of elaboration that a customer decides to buy any product through digesting a message which is directly proportional to the persuasiveness of that communication. However, this study further focuses on the demography of young users in Bangladesh who are comparably maximum influenced by social media marketing. The criteria for the unit of analysis are: first, Bangladeshi young users age limit is between 18 to 30; and second, who purchase their products in online platform. These younger customers purchase the items offered for sale on various online marketplaces, such as Daraz, BD shop, Evaly, Ubay, and ShopZ BD, among others. Thus, the objective of this study is to investigate

the influence of social media marketing on purchase intention of young customers. In the next part of this study, the theoretical background, literature, and hypotheses development. The third part explains the methodology, fourth part includes analysis and discussion. Finally, this study ends with implication, limitation, and conclusion.

2. Literature review

2.1. Underlying theory

To comprehend the relationship between SMM and young consumers' purchase intention, and to develop the present theoretical framework, this study followed the Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM), which has been initiated by Petty and Cacioppo (1986). The ELM proposes that the persuasiveness of a message depends on the level of elaboration (thinking) a consumer devotes to processing it. Based on this concept, we anticipate that influence of social media content, engagement and interaction, brand awareness and perception, and influencer marketing may have impact on social media platforms that ultimately lead to higher message elaboration among young consumers. This elaboration process can in turn strengthen brand awareness, trust, and positive brand associations, ultimately influencing purchase intention. Additionally, social interaction and engagement on social media platforms can further enhance message elaboration by exposing young consumers to diverse perspectives and opinions about products or services.

2.2. Purchase intention

Previously, several studies indicated that factors such as entertainment, interaction, and word of mouth in the social media platforms strongly influence purchase intention of the customers. For example, Kumar *et al.* (2020) revealed that there is an accountable role of social media marketing on buying choices of the customer. Similarly, Fajri *et al.* (2021) showed a beneficial impact of social media marketing on both raising brand awareness and influencing purchasing choices. Therefore, businesses should effectively utilize media platforms to improve their marketing strategies and engage with customers to drive their intention to shop online. Emini and Zeqiri (2021) highlighted the role of brand awareness and brand engagement in a transitioning economy emphasizing the importance of elements in understanding how social media marketing influences purchase intention. Another study by Heidari *et al.* (2023) found that social media marketing significantly influences brand equity, customer attachment, to brands, trust, and intentions to make purchases.

The present research emphasizes the effects of social media marketing on consumer related factors. In another similar research, Shadi *et al.* (2021) explored how social media marketing strategies are related to customer response considering the influence of brand equity factors. Moreover, Ramadhani and Prasasti (2023) and Heidari *et al.* (2023) emphasized the positive influence of social media marketing initiatives on purchase intention by means of factors such as brand trust and brand equity. In addition, Putri (2021) also highlighted the impact of social media marketing on consumer purchase intentions by emphasizing the exchange facilitated by social media platforms, between businesses and customers.

2.3. Influence of social media content

Several studies highlight the positive influence of engaging and well-crafted social media content on young consumers' purchase behavior. Shadi *et al.* (2021) explored the relationship between social media marketing strategies and customer response, emphasizing the importance of content that impacts brand equity factors. Engaging content, as discussed by Putri (2021), can spark interest in products and services, while features like sharing and personalized recommendations (Sansern *et al.*, 2022) can further enhance brand perception and trust. Additionally, studies by Karunasingha and Abeysekera (2022) and Shafaat *et al.* (2020) demonstrate how content marketing strategies can influence purchase decisions in specific contexts, such as the fashion industry. These findings suggest that businesses can leverage high-quality,

engaging content marketing strategies on social media platforms to positively influence young consumers' online purchase behavior. Based on the above literature support, we propose the following hypothesis:

H1: *There is a positive association between the influence of social media content and purchase intention.*

2.4. Engagement and interaction

The interactive nature of social media platforms plays a crucial role in influencing young consumers' online purchase decisions. Studies by Wijayaa *et al.* (2021) and Shien *et al.* (2023) highlight the positive correlation between social engagement and the desire of young consumers to make purchases. User-generated content, engagement, interaction, and positive word-of-mouth recommendations (Othman & Rahim, 2019), and interactive features like comments and reviews can all influence purchase decisions. Moreover, Heidari *et al.* (2023) suggest that engaging content and features can foster customer brand attachment, which can contribute to positive purchase behavior. These studies emphasize the importance of fostering social interaction and engagement on social media platforms to influence young consumers' online purchase behavior. That is why we propose the following hypothesis:

H2: *There is a positive association between engagement and interaction and purchase intention of young consumers.*

2.5. Brand awareness and perception

Building brand awareness and a positive brand perception are crucial aspects of SMM that can significantly influence young consumers' online purchase intention. Studies by Fajri *et al.* (2021), Emini and Zeqiri (2021), and Heidari *et al.* (2023) demonstrate the positive impact of social media marketing on brand awareness, trust, and brand equity, ultimately influencing purchase intention. Social media activities can help businesses connect with young consumers, create brand recognition, and foster positive brand associations. Additionally, Ramadhani and Prasasti (2023) and Heidari *et al.* (2023) highlight the role of brand trust in influencing purchase intention through social media marketing initiatives. These findings suggest that businesses can utilize SMM to build brand awareness, trust, and a positive brand image, ultimately influencing young consumers' online purchase behavior. Nevertheless, Hsiao *et al.* (2010) uncovered that trust in product recommendations is influenced by perceived ability, benevolence or integrity critical mass perception and trust in a website, the level of trust subsequently affects customers inclination to make purchases. Similar other scholars such as Zhang *et al.* (2023), Raees *et al.* (2023), Lopes *et al.* (2023), and Sansern *et al.* (2022) discovered that social media marketing influences on consumer's decision-making process when they shop online, because the consumers see the advertising on the relevant product, they are more likely to buy it. Moreover, scholars have explored how social media marketing impacts consumers inclination to make purchases in contexts, such as the fashion industry (Karunasingha & Abeysekera, 2022; Shafaat *et al.*, 2020) luxury brands (Natiqa *et al.*, 2022) and specific platforms like Facebook Live (Sansern *et al.*, 2022). These studies have revealed that trust, brand awareness and brand engagement play a role in linking social media marketing to purchase intention.

H3: *There is a positive association between brand awareness and perception and purchase intention of young consumers.*

2.6. Influencer marketing impact

Influencer marketing has been identified as a significant aspect of social media marketing that influences purchase intention among young consumers. Research has demonstrated that influencer marketing activities have a positive impact on brand equity, e-WOM distribution, and customers' purchase intention (Aji *et al.*, 2020). The involvement of influencers in live streaming e-commerce has been recognized as a mechanism that enhances consumer purchase intention through trust and attachment (Chen & Yang,

2023). Moreover, studies have shown that influencer credibility and the disclosure of advertisements can positively affect purchase intention (Sesar *et al.*, 2022). Factors such as perceived influencer credibility, product-customer relevance, entertainment value of influencer content, influencer expertise, and peer reviews are crucial in shaping the purchase intentions of Gen Z consumers (Nguyen *et al.*, 2022). Additionally, the mediating role of customer satisfaction between digital marketing practices and purchase intention has been underscored (Dash & Chakraborty, 2021). Overall, influencer marketing, in conjunction with social media marketing, customer engagement, and brand trust, significantly influences the purchase intentions of young consumers, underscoring the importance of these elements in contemporary marketing strategies.

H4: *There is a positive association between influencer marketing impact and purchase intention of young consumers.*

3. Framework of the study

The main purpose for this study is to identify the relationship between influence of social media content (i.e. influence of social media content, engagement and interaction, brand awareness, and influencer marketing impact), and the purchasing intentions of young consumers. Based on the objective of this study and literature support, the present research proposes the following framework in the Figure 1:

4. Materials and methods

The research applied a quantitative approach with a cross-sectional study based on the recommendation of Cooper and Schindler (2014). A cross-sectional sample survey is implemented in the research for obtaining data at a particular point during time (Sekaran & Bougie, 2010). This study used cross-sectional data because of its convenient accessibility. Respondents were chosen to ensure data collection accuracy based on their willingness to offer their data. Ensuring data accuracy in Bangladesh's nationwide data collection is challenging due to the country's large population and conservative culture. Purposive sampling is used in this research for two additional purposes. Initially, as highlighted by Chen *et al.* (2022), the task of collecting and preserving the whole population roster posed significant difficulties. Moreover, many participants are reluctant to divulge personal data or opinions due to apprehensions about privacy. Besides, this approach is more cost-effective, which is a significant consideration for funding for this study. Furthermore, the use of data in an effective manner is made simpler and more readily available (Malhotra & Dash, 2017). Nevertheless, the purposive selection technique prioritizes characteristics of data, leading to precise and reliable research findings (Cooper & Schindler, 2014). The researchers used selective sampling to fulfil their study's objective of predicting and illustrating correlations between variables rather than making sweeping generalizations about the whole population.

However, five items were utilized to evaluate each of the four key elements of social media marketing as independent variables in the present research. Among those, 'influence of social media' content five item has been collected from Shien *et al.* (2023); 'engagement and interaction'

Figure 1. PartLabel-upper Conceptual Framework; Source: Researcher's own creation.

three items from Emini and Zeqiri (2021) and two items from Bilgin (2018); 'brand awareness and perception' five items from Emini and Zeqiri (2021); 'influencer marketing impact' five items from Bilgin (2018). The dependent variable, purchase intention, is composed of five items designed by Shien *et al.* (2023). A Likert scale with five points that includes 'strongly agree' to 'strongly disagree' was used for assessing both the independent and dependent variables. The questionnaire has been shown in Appendix-1.

The current study specifically focused on the demography of young users in Bangladesh who are influenced by social media marketing, considering them as the 'target population'. The selection criteria for the unit of analysis were individuals who are Bangladeshi young users age limit is between 18 to 30; and who purchase their products in online platform or, social media or, e-commerce platforms. In accordance with the local context and perspective, we have defined a maximum age of 30 years as being considered youthful. These youthful consumers purchase the items that are purchased on several online platforms such as Daraz, BD shop, Evaly, Ubay, and ShopZ BD. We have chosen certain items and online stores for our research, targeting youthful consumers' preferences. Additionally, customers were also deliberately picked for the study. Thus, researchers in this study used purposive sampling to ensure they carefully considered the inclusion criteria when choosing individuals. The inclusion criteria for selecting the respondents of this study were, firstly, Bangladeshi young users age limit is between 18 to 30; and secondly, who purchase their products in online platform.

Moreover, before conduction the survey, the researchers applied to the 'Research Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Business and Economics of the University of Debrecen' for ethical certificate attaching the questionnaire, sampling details, and ethical considerations. After assessing all ethical concerns and guidelines the committee approved and provided the certificate for further survey process. Moreover, before data was collected from any participant, their written consent was obtained, and they were adequately informed about the purpose of the research. Thus, written consent was obtained from each individual respondent in this study.

The investigators of the present research used a method of non-probability sampling known as 'purposive sampling'. Most motivated youthful people participating to studies in online shopping in Bangladesh are among the age of 18 to 30 (Hasan *et al.*, 2022). The explanation for using the purposive sampling method in this research derives from two reasons: firstly, the total number of participants is undetermined and secondly, the representative population is unavailable (Chen *et al.*, 2022). Furthermore, purposive sampling is beneficial because of cost-effectiveness, simplicity, and timesaving (Malhotra & Dash, 2017).

The researchers used G*power tests to ascertain the appropriate sample size based on the suggestion of Faul *et al.* (2009). Furthermore, Mumtaz *et al.* (2017) and Hair *et al.* (2021) have emphasized the significance of using power analysis to determine the suitable sample size in social science research. According to the G*power analysis, a research model with three components requires a minimum sample size of 77. This criterion is based on a medium effect size of 15, with 80% power and a 5% significance threshold, as stated by Faul *et al.* (2009). Malhotra and Dash (2017) suggest that it is advisable to evaluate each variable using a minimum of three items or scales while doing structural equation modelling. Additionally, it is preferable for the commonality to be at least 0.5. In addition, Malhotra and Dash (2017) proposed that a minimum sample size of 200 is deemed satisfactory for conducting a structural equation modelling study. This study included evaluating four independent variables, each of which was assessed using five items. Similarly, the dependent variable was also examined using five things. Given the guidelines mentioned above and the debates, the researchers in this study posit that a sample size of over 200 is suitable for progressing to the subsequent stage.

Moreover, we sent 500 questionnaires and got 431 responses in return. After careful examination, we observed 412 valid and properly filled up responses. 82.4 percent of respondents are considered acceptable according to the current research by Baruch & Holtom, (2008). Previously, Mobarak Karim *et al.* (2023) could achieve 79%, Shahneaz *et al.* (2020) 77.9%, Mahmud *et al.* (2022) 47.2%, and Amin and Rubel (2020) 44.37% response rate in context of Bangladesh. Therefore, for the purpose of our final study, we assume that evaluating a total of 412 different samples of data is empirically acceptable.

5. Results

5.1. Demographic profile

Table 1 shows the demographic data of those who participated classified into 3 separate age classifications: 18-20, 21-23, and 24 and older. The results demonstrate many of the respondents belong within the age range of 21 to 23 (230). Additionally, the survey shows there are only 115 participants aged between 18 and 20, however there are 67 respondents aged 24 and above. This suggests that a larger proportion of Bangladesh's a younger generation is enthusiastic about using online shopping. The following Table 1 shows the demographic data of the respondents:

Table 1 illustrates the dissemination of education phases, with a greater percentage of the population having a graduate's degree or higher. There are a few additional criteria toward whom the grades of Diploma-100 and Postgraduate-74 can be comparable. On the other hand, there are 31 of those who are married, while 381 individuals who are single. Both married and unmarried people in Bangladesh demonstrate an intense interest in using e-commerce, shown by the marriage percentage. A total of 115 respondents had 4-6 years of experience utilizing online shopping, while 216 individuals had 1-3 years of experience had been stated by some individuals, whereas 81 individuals had 7 or more years of experience. using e-commerce. It is expected that the impartial participants had an extensive knowledge of how users from all age groups, levels of experience, and marital conditions assess online shopping.

5.2. Measurement and structural models

Regarding data collection, a confirmatory factor analysis, or CFA, was used to assess the validity and reliability of the variables implemented in this research. The investigation examined the loading assessments, typical variation obtained, and overall reliability of each item as indicators of convergence validity. Table 2 illustrates that the initial score for each indicator exceeds the required threshold levels of 0.60 provided by Vinzi *et al.* (2010) and 0.07 recommended by Hair *et al.* (2021). Hence, the researchers excluded items with low leading scores, namely BAP5 (0.523), EI1 (0.631), and IMI3 (0.249), due to their scores falling below the threshold of 0.70. In addition, the AVE and CR values of all the constructs proved suitable if they surpassed the threshold values of 0.5 and 0.7, as recommended by Hair *et al.* (2013). Additionally, the composite dependability scores for each component reached the threshold of 0.70. The following Table 2 represents measurement model of this study to justify its reliability and validity:

The discriminant validity in this research was examined utilizing the HTMT method. Based on the recommendation of Henseler *et al.* (2015), the HTMT criterion in this investigation surpassed the Fornell and Larcker (1981) criterion, as shown in Table 3. Furthermore, this study conducted an HTMT analysis in Table 4, which indicates that all HTMT values are below the threshold (0.850) suggested by Henseler *et al.* (2015). Therefore, all the fundamental factors were identified and found appropriate for additional examination. As a result, the measurement model is appropriate for the analysis of the research, supporting the dependability as well as the precision of the hypotheses. The following Table 3 shows the values from the Discriminant Validity, i.e. Fornell-Larcker Criterion of this research:

Table 1. Demographic profile of the participants.

Variables	Description	Frequency	Percentage
Age	18-20 years	115	27.92%
	21-23 years	230	55.82%
	24 & above	67	16.26%
Education	Diploma	100	24.27%
	Graduate	238	57.76%
	Postgraduate	74	17.96%
Gender	Male	202	49.02%
	Female	210	50.97%
Experience	1 to 3 years	216	52.42%
	4 to 6 years	115	27.91%
	7 & above	81	19.66%
Marital Status	Married	31	7.52%
	Unmarried	381	92.47%

Table 2. Output of the measurement model.

Construct	Items	Loadings	CR	AVE	Cronbach's Alpha
Brand Awareness and Perception (BAP)	BAP1: Brand awareness is easier through social media	0.903	0.947	0.817	0.926
	BAP2: Social media offer more characteristics about brands	0.918			
	BAP3: Brands through social media are easily remembered	0.918			
	BAP4: Social media helps me recognize brands	0.877			
Engagement and Interaction (EI)	EI2: I get engaged through social media in brand activities	0.703	0.901	0.696	0.850
	EI3: Social media makes me feel positive toward a brand	0.775			
	EI4: Discussion and exchange of opinions is possible on social media page of brands	0.919			
	EI5: The expression of opinions is easy on social media of brands	0.920			
	IM1: I like the ads about the brands have published on social media	0.771			
Influencer Marketing Impact (IMI)	IM2: The ads about brands released on social media are interesting	0.901	0.919	0.741	0.888
	IM4: The influencer marketing is trustworthy	0.883			
Influence of Social Media Content (ISMC)	IM5: The influencer marketing is a reliable approach	0.881	0.885	0.607	0.838
	ISM1: Social media makes my life easier	0.749			
	ISM2: Social media sites help me to increase my knowledge about the products, services, and brands	0.816			
	ISM3: Social media sites provide accurate and proper knowledge of products and services	0.882			
	ISM4: Social media marketing inspires me to make a buying decision	0.727			
	ISM5: I am satisfied with the social media marketing of brands that I follow	0.708			
Purchase Intention (PI)	PI1: I tend to make decisions better on using social media sites of brands before purchasing goods and services	0.848	0.928	0.722	0.903
	PI2: I have more interest in buying products and services when using social media sites	0.883			
	PI3: I am very likely to purchase products or services recommended by my friends on social media sites	0.888			
	PI4: I expect to purchase products as marketed on brand's social media sites that I follow	0.821			
	PI5: I intend to purchase products as marketed on brand's social media sites that I follow	0.804			

Note. EI1: 'I have a close relation on social media with those who use the same brands'; BAP5: 'Information from social media help in brand awareness and perception'; IMI3: 'Social media ads of brands positively affect my attention for the brand' had to be removed because of poor loading.

Table 3. Discriminant validity (Fornell-Larcker Criterion).

	BAP	EI	IMI	ISMC	PI
BAP	0.904				
EI	0.153	0.834			
IMI	0.227	0.148	0.861		
ISMC	0.236	0.218	0.317	0.779	
PI	0.289	0.270	0.270	0.344	0.850

Note. ISMC=Influence of Social Media Content, EI=Engagement and Interaction, BAP=Brand awareness and perception, IMI=Influencer marketing impact, PI=Purchase intention.

Moreover, the following **Table 4** represents the values from the Discriminant Validity through Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) Ratio:

Researchers exploited Smart-PLS version 4 to analyze the conceptual framework as well as investigate the hypothesized connections. The capacity for explanation of the study's model has been measured by R2 values. The research found that the R2 value for the predictor's explanation power on the result of the model, PI, was 0.211. This indicates that the variables ISMC, EI, BAP, and IMI collectively explain 21.1% of the variance in PI.

Table 4. Discriminant validity Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) Ratio.

	BAP	EI	IMI	ISMC	PI
BAP					
EI	0.174				
IMI	0.247	0.164			
ISMC	0.274	0.258	0.366		
PI	0.307	0.307	0.275	0.378	

Note. ISMC=Influence of Social Media Content, EI=Engagement and Interaction, BAP=Brand awareness and perception, IMI=Influencer marketing impact, PI=Purchase intention.

Table 5. Predictive relevance of the path model.

Dependent Variables	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Q ² Values
Purchase Intension	0.211	0.204	0.575

Table 6. VIF values for constructs.

	BAP	EI	IMI	ISMC	PI
BAP					1.098
EI					1.067
IMI					1.149
ISMC					1.180
PI					

Note. ISMC=Influence of Social Media Content, EI=Engagement and Interaction, BAP=Brand awareness and perception, IMI=Influencer marketing impact, PI=Purchase intention.

Furthermore, the blindfolding procedure was utilized with an omission distance of 7 for the purpose of measuring the predictive significance of the path model. Stone-Geisser's (Stone, 1974; Geisser, 1974) Q² value for the endogenous construct has been determined above zero (Q²_{PI} = 0.575) in Table 5, demonstrating sufficient cross-validated predictive validity of the route model (Hair *et al.*, 2021). The following Table 5 demonstrates the results from predictive relevance of the path model:

Further, the research observed that the VIF values in Table 6 for all structures were below 3.3, showing the lack of multicollinearity concerns (Mahmud *et al.*, 2022). The following Table 6 shoes the VIF values for the constructs:

A bootstrapping method with 5000 subsamples was conducted to determine the path coefficients' weights and significance using a one-tailed approach (Hair *et al.*, 2021). The paths from BAP to PI, EI to PI, IMI to PI, and ISMC to PI are positively and significantly associated, as shown in Table 7 ($\beta=0.180, 0.175, 0.133, \text{ and } 0.222$ respectively; $p<0.05$). Thus, H1, H2, H3, and H4 all indicated statistically significant relationships. The results from the hypotheses testing are shown in the Table 7 below:

The results of the research showed that a positive sense of organizational performance is improved by greater levels of organizational, environmental, individual, and influencer marketing impact in managing aviation risks. The following Figure 2 shows the measurement model with p values:

Additionally, the following Figure 3 shows the measurement model with t values.

6. Discussion

The results of the regression study indicates that hypothesis 1, expressing that social media contents has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention, has been confirmed at a 5% significance level ($\beta=0.180$; $p<0.05$). The results align with the studies conducted by Sanny *et al.* (2020) and Putri and Tiarawati (2021). Social media content usually impacts purchase intentions by promoting products while providing specific objectives for users to achieve their goals. These behaviors assist in the development of organizational knowledge, skills, and talents.

The second hypothesis is embraced based on the regression analysis at an acceptable level of significance of 5%, with a beta coefficient of 0.175 and a p-value less than 0.05, suggesting that interaction and involvement significantly improve the intention to buy. According to this study, organizations have a strong desire to encourage environmentally conscious behavior from managers when they desire to

Table 7. Hypotheses testing (direct effects).

Hypotheses	Paths	Std. Beta	Std. Error	T Statistics	P Values	Decisions
H1	BAP → PI	0.180	0.180	3.787	0.000	Significant
H2	EI → PI	0.175	0.179	3.788	0.000	Significant
H3	IMI → PI	0.133	0.132	2.989	0.003	Significant
H4	ISMC → PI	0.222	0.225	4.399	0.000	Significant

Note. ISMC=Influence of social media content, EI=Engagement and Interaction, BAP=Brand awareness and perception, IMI=Influencer marketing impact, PI=Purchase intention.

Figure 2. PartLabel-upper Measurement model including p values; Source: Generated from PLS 4 software.

improve their knowledge, skills, and abilities. Kaveh *et al.* (2021) and Habib *et al.* (2022) support this finding. Environmentally conscious executives may motivate employees to excel by integrating their work with meaning and guidance. They may develop a powerful goal for their employees or organization to connect corporate objectives and improve buy intention, involvement, and commitment.

The third hypothesis is accepted: brand awareness, perception, and purchase intention have a positive correlation at a level of significance of 5% ($\beta=0.133$; $p<0.05$). Brand awareness as well as perception play an essential part in encouraging organizations to increase their performance. The outcomes of regression have connections to previous research investigations. Brand awareness and perception highly impact an organization and its buying intention through allowing members to make contributions to decision-making by offering new ideas and knowledge (Emini & Zeqiri, 2021; Setiari & Ekawati, 2022).

The fourth hypothesis indicates that influencer marketing impacts purchase intention. The findings demonstrate that influencer marketing has a positively and statistically significant impact on purchase intention at a significance level of 5% ($\beta=0.222$; $p<0.05$). This finding corresponds to previous research. Influencer marketing affect is an important component of organizational loyalty that supports organizations by improving their knowledge, talents, and skills, so that it impacts their work performance (Aggad & Ahmad, 2021).

Organizational involvement is essential for the growth and development of added value in a company. The regression study reveals that there is a significant connection between organizational, environmental, individual, and influencer marketing influences and purchase intention. This investigation

Figure 3. PartLabel-upper Measurement model including t values; Source: Generated from PLS 4 software.

improves comprehension of the complicated impact of organizational, environmental, individual, and influencer marketing factors on purchase intention.

7. Implications

This study investigated that there is a positive relationship between social media marketing and purchase intention among young customers in Bangladesh. Business strategically leveraging the different factors of social media marketing which are (influence of social media content, engagement and interaction, brand awareness and perception, and influencer marketing impact) to improve their online footprint and motivate customer purchase intention. In addition, focusing on these attributes delivers a unique effect: it not only impacts the customer purchase intention, but it additionally improves capacity for organization and effectiveness. This research contributes to the growing body of knowledge on the young generation's online shopping behavior. By analyzing the specific SMM dimensions influencing their purchase intention (content, engagement, brand awareness, influencer marketing), the study provides a deeper understanding of how this demographic interacts with social media and makes online purchase decisions. Businesses targeting young people online shoppers can leverage the study's findings to develop more effective SMM strategies. Focusing on creating engaging social media content, fostering interactive experiences, building positive brand awareness, and collaborating with relevant influencers can significantly impact their purchase decisions. By implementing these SMM strategies informed by the research, businesses can potentially improve their online marketing return on investment by reaching and converting a key demographic (young generation) more effectively. Moreover, Stakeholders can use the suggested strategy to modify their advertising strategies particularly for these consumers, to make use of the highlighted components that affect their purchasing decisions. The findings are valuable for various stakeholders, including marketing managers, social media strategists, and e-commerce platform developers. By understanding the importance of specific SMM dimensions for young people, these stakeholders can tailor their advertising strategies, social media features, and online shopping experiences to better cater to this crucial demographic.

8. Limitation

There are some limitations for this research, and these may motivate future research studies. One of the limitations is the number of variables was limited, and future research may consider more variables. Another limitation is the method that has been used in this research was only quantitative (survey), for the future research to be more strengthened may they use qualitative method such as face observation or focus group discussion. Because of unavailability of the sampling frame, this study used purposive sampling, which is a non-probability sampling. Future researchers can use any probability sampling method in their study. Finally, it was a cross-sectional study whereas, future scholars can focus on longitudinal research.

9. Conclusions

This study investigated the relationship between social media marketing (SMM) and purchase intention among young consumers in Bangladesh. The findings reveal that all four SMM dimensions analyzed (content, engagement, brand awareness, influencer marketing) have a positive impact on young consumers' purchase decisions. This research contributes to a deeper understanding of young population' online shopping behavior and highlights the crucial role of specific SMM elements in influencing their purchase intentions. By leveraging these findings, businesses can develop more effective SMM strategies to reach and convert this important demographic. Furthermore, this research adds to the growing knowledge base on the evolving landscape of online marketing and consumer behavior in the digital age.

Ethical approval and guideline

The survey of the research has been approved by the 'Research Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Business and Economics of the University of Debrecen'. The Commission approved the research design by decision GTK-KB 002-01/2023, which did not raise any ethical objections.

Participant's consent

The respondents were well informed about the objective of this study and before collecting data from them, the consent was confirmed from each of the participants. The researcher collected written consent from all individual participants.

Authors' contributions

All authors contributed to the study's conception, design, and execution. Material preparation, data collection, formal analysis, and interpretation were performed by Mohammad Bin Amin and Mohammed Julfikar Ali. Key Supervision and literature writing were performed by Ismael Awaz Shukri and Balogh Péter. The background of the study and hypothesis building was done by Ismael Awaz Shukri, Mohammad Bin Amin and Zita Hajdú. The first draft of the manuscript was written by Ismael Awaz Shukri, Zita Hajdú, Mohammed Julfikar Ali, Mohammad Bin Amin, and Balogh Péter. All authors read, reviewed, agreed, and approved the final and submission version of the manuscript. All authors agreed and confirmed that they would accept all corrections during revision, that the final version would be accepted for publication, and that any significant changes would be introduced at the proofing stage. Finally, all authors agreed to take responsibility for the accuracy or integrity of the published work and be accountable for the contents of the article.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

Data availability declaration

The data will be available to the correspondence author upon reasonable demand.

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References

- Aggad, K., & Ahmad, F. (2021). Investigates the impact of social media influencers' personality, content, and trustworthiness on consumers' purchase intention and ewom. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 11(12), 2368–2384. <https://doi.org/10.6007/IJARBS/v11-i12/11782>
- Aji, P., Nadhila, V., & Sanny, L. (2020). Effect of social media marketing on Instagram towards purchase intention: Evidence from Indonesia's ready-to-drink tea industry. *International Journal of Data and Network Science*, 4(2), 91–104. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.ijdns.2020.3.002>

- Amin, M. B., & Rubel, M. R. B. (2020). Human resource management practices and employee knowledge sharing behavior: Mediating role of knowledge sharing intention. *Asian Journal of Empirical Research*, 10(5), 150–164. <https://doi.org/10.18488/journal.1007/2020.10.5/1007.5.150.164>
- Baruch, Y., & Holtom, B. C. (2008). Survey response rate levels and trends in organizational research. *Human Relations*, 61(8), 1139–1160. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0018726708094863>
- Bilgin, Y. (2018). The effect of social media marketing activities on brand awareness, brand image and brand loyalty. *Business & Management Studies: An International Journal*, 6(1), 128–148.
- Cabales, J. H., Carungay, N. K., Legaspi, K. K., Bacatan, R. J., & Bacatan, J. (2023). The influence of social media marketing on customer purchasing behavior of senior high school students. *Quest Journals Journal of Research in Business and Management*, 11(10), 74–80.
- Chanthinok, K., Ussahawanitichakit, P., & Jhundra-indra, P. (2015, July). Social media marketing strategy and marketing outcomes: A conceptual framework. In Allied Academies International Conference. *Academy of Marketing Studies. Proceedings* (Vol. 20, No. 2, p. 35). Jordan Whitney Enterprises, Inc.
- Chen, G., Pine, D. S., Brotman, M. A., Smith, A. R., Cox, R. W., Taylor, P. A., & Haller, S. P. (2022). Hyperbolic trade-off: The importance of balancing trial and subject sample sizes in neuroimaging. *NeuroImage*, 247, 118786. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2021.118786>
- Chen, N., & Yang, Y. (2023). The role of influencers in live streaming e-commerce: Influencer trust, attachment, and consumer purchase intention. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research*, 18(3), 1601–1618. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jtaer18030081>
- Cooper, D. R., & Schindler, P. (2014). *Business research methods* (12th ed.). McGraw Hill International Edition.
- Dash, G., & Chakraborty, D. (2021). Digital transformation of marketing strategies during a pandemic: Evidence from an emerging economy during covid-19. *Sustainability*, 13(12), 6735. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13126735>
- Emini, A., & Zeqiri, J. (2021). The impact of social media marketing on purchase intention in a transition economy: The mediating role of brand awareness and brand engagement. *ENTRENOVA - ENTerprise REsearch InNOVation*, 7(1), 262–272. <https://doi.org/10.54820/FDOR9238>
- Fajri, I., Rizkyanfi, M., & Smaya, R. (2021). The effect of social media marketing on purchase decisions with brand awareness as an intervening variable in Praketa coffee shop Purwokerto. *The Journal Gastronomy Tourism*, 8(2), 97–110. <https://doi.org/10.17509/gastur.v8i2.41922>
- Fornell, C., & Larcker, D. F. (1981). Structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error: Algebra and statistics. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 18(3), 382–388. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3150980>
- Faul, F., Erdfelder, E., Buchner, A., & Lang, A. G. (2009). Statistical power analyses using G* Power 3.1: Tests for correlation and regression analyses. *Behavior Research Methods*, 41(4), 1149–1160.
- Garg, A., & Kumar, J. (2021). Social media marketing influence on Boutique Hotel customers' purchase intention in Malaysia. *Tourism & Management Studies*, 17(3), 51–62. <https://doi.org/10.18089/tms.2021.170304>
- Geisser, S. (1974). A predictive approach to the random effect model. *Biometrika*, 61(1), 101–107. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biomet/61.1.101>
- Gruzd, A., Wellman, B., & Takhteyev, Y. (2011). Imagining Twitter as an imagined community. *American Behavioral Scientist*, 55(10), 1294–1318. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002764211409378>
- Habib, S., Hamadneh, N., & Hassan, A. (2022). The relationship between digital marketing, customer engagement, and purchase intention via OTT platforms. *Journal of Mathematics*, 2022(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/5327626>
- Hair, J. F., Jr, Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., Sarstedt, M., Danks, N. P., & Ray, S. (2021). *Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) using R: A workbook* (p. 197). Springer Nature.
- Hair, J. F., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2013). Partial least squares structural equation modeling: Rigorous applications, better results and higher acceptance. *Long Range Planning*, 46(1–2), 1–12.
- Hasan, I., Habib, M. M., & Tewari, V. (2022). Factors affecting the online purchasing behavior for young consumers: A case study. *Journal of Service Science and Management*, 15(05), 531–550. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jssm.2022.155031>
- Heidari, S., Zarei, M., Daneshfar, A., & Dokhanian, S. (2023). Increasing sales through social media marketing: The role of customer brand attachment, brand trust, and brand equity. *Marketing and Management of Innovations*, 14(1), 224–234. <https://doi.org/10.21272/mmi.2023.1-19>
- Henseler, J., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2015). A new criterion for assessing discriminant validity in variance-based structural equation modeling. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 43(1), 115–135. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11747-014-0403-8>
- Hsiao, K., Lin, J., Wang, X., Lu, H., & Yu, H. (2010). Antecedents and consequences of trust in online product recommendations. *Online Information Review*, 34(6), 935–953. <https://doi.org/10.1108/14684521011099414>
- Islam, M. T., Pradhan, B., & Kumar, J. (2024). Social media reviews' influence on spa and wellness consumer choices: Conceptual framework, prospective significance, and future research directions. In *Utilizing smart technology and AI in hybrid tourism and hospitality* (pp. 1–22). IGI Global.
- Karunasingha, A., & Abeysekera, N. (2022). The mediating effect of trust on consumer behavior in social media marketing environments. *South Asian Journal of Marketing*, 3(2), 135–149. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SAJM-10-2021-0126>
- Kaveh, A., Nazari, M., Rest, J., & Mira, S. (2021). Customer engagement in sales promotion. *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, 39(3), 424–437. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MIP-11-2019-0582>

- Khan, S.K., & Bhutto, S.A. (2023). Paradigm shift to social media marketing impacting consumer purchase intention in the restaurant industry. *International Journal of Social Science & Entrepreneurship*, 3(2), 112–136. <https://doi.org/10.58661/ijssse.v3i2.135>
- Kula, T. Ismail, K., & Ibrahim, S. A. (2021). Consumer's motivation toward purchase intention on online product with mediating effect of trust in Brunei. *Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Studies*, 04(09), 1804–1811. <https://doi.org/10.47191/jefms/v4-i9-27>
- Kumar, J., Konar, R., & Balasubramanian, K. (2020). The impact of social media on consumers' purchasing behaviour in Malaysian Restaurants. *Journal of Tourism, Sustainability and Well-Being*, 8(3), 197–216.
- Lopes, P., Rodrigues, R. H., Sandes, F. S., & Estrela, R. (2023). The moderating role of social media advertising in customers' purchase intention. *European Conference on Social Media*, 10(1), 117–124. <https://doi.org/10.34190/ecsm.10.1.1205>
- Mahmud, A., Ding, D., Hasan, M., Ali, Z., & Amin, M. B. (2022). Employee psychological reactions to micro-corporate social responsibility and societal behavior: A structural equation modeling analysis. *Current Psychology (New Brunswick, N.J.)*, 42(20), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-022-02898-2>
- Malhotra, K., & Dash, S. (2017). *Marketing research, an applied orientation*, 7E (pp. 01–767). Dorling Kindersley (India) PVT. LTD.
- Mobarak Karim, M., Bin Amin, M., Ahmed, H., Hajdu, Z., & Popp, J. (2023). The influence of leadership styles on employee performance in telecom companies of Bangladesh. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 21(3), 671–681. [https://doi.org/10.21511/ppm.21\(3\).2023.52](https://doi.org/10.21511/ppm.21(3).2023.52)
- Moslehpour, M., Dadvari, A., Nugroho, W., & Do, B. (2020). The dynamic stimulus of social media marketing on purchase intention of Indonesian airline products and services. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*, 33(2), 561–583. <https://doi.org/10.1108/APJML-07-2019-0442>
- Mumtaz, A. M., Ting, H., Ramayah, T., Chuah, F., & Cheah, J. H. (2017). Editorial; a review of the methodological misconceptions and guidelines related to the application of structural equation modelling: a Malaysian scenario. *Journal of Applied Structural Equation Modeling*, 1(1), 1–13.
- Natiqa, D., Kusumawati, N., & Aprilianty, F. (2022) *The effect of instagram on customer relationship, customer equity, and purchase intention towards luxury fashion brands* [Paper presentation]. <https://doi.org/10.4108/eai.27-7-2021.2316834>
- Nguyen, C., Nguyen, T., & Luu, V. (2022). Relationship between influencer marketing and purchase intention: Focusing on Vietnamese gen Z consumers. *Independent Journal of Management & Production*, 13(2), 810–828. <https://doi.org/10.14807/ijmp.v13i2.1603>
- Nibir, M. M. A. M., Saha, D. R., & Islam, S. A. (2024). *Influence of Social media advertisements on purchasing intention: A web-based cross-sectional study on the students of Khulna University, Bangladesh*. Khulna University Studies.
- Othman, R., & Rahim, M. K. I. A. (2019). The impact of online purchase intentions caused by electronic word of mouth. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 9(2), 1132–1141. <https://doi.org/10.6007/IJARBS/v9-i2/5670>
- Owusu Yeboah, A. Y., Kwarteng, M. A., & Novak, P. (2024). Social media marketing, value creation and firm's sustainability performance: A study among young consumers. *Aslib Journal of Information Management*, 76(2), 248–268. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AJIM-05-2022-0245>
- Peighambari, K., Sattari, S., Kordestani, A., & Oghazi, P. (2016). Consumer behavior research: A synthesis of the recent literature. *Sage Open*, 6(2), 2158244016645638. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244016645638>
- Petty, R. E., & Cacioppo, J. T. (1986). *The elaboration likelihood model of persuasion* (pp. 1–24). Springer.
- Putri, D. (2021). Digital marketing strategy to increase brand awareness and customer purchase intention (case study: Ailesh green consulting). *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, 6(5), 87–93. <https://doi.org/10.24018/ejbmr.2021.6.5.1063>
- Putri, F., & Tiawati, M. (2021). The effect of social media influencer and brand image on online purchase intention during the Covid-19 pandemic. *Ilomata International Journal of Management*, 2(3), 163–171. <https://doi.org/10.52728/ijjm.v2i3.261>
- Qalati, S. A., Vela, E. G., Li, W., Dakhan, S. A., Hong Thuy, T. T., & Merani, S. H. (2021). Effects of perceived service quality, website quality, and reputation on purchase intention: The mediating and moderating roles of trust and perceived risk in online shopping. *Cogent Business & Management*, 8(1), 1869363. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2020.1869363>
- Raees, M., Khan, S.K., & Zaheer, K. (2023). Impact of social media marketing on consumer purchase intention: A SEM based study of attitude towards information. *International Journal of Social Science & Entrepreneurship*, 3(2), 523–544. <https://doi.org/10.58661/ijssse.v3i2.153>
- Ramadhani, J., & Prasasti, A. (2023). Brand trust capacity in mediating social media marketing activities and purchase intention: a case of a local brand that go-global during pandemic. *Indonesian Journal of Business and Entrepreneurship (IJBE)*, 9(1), 81–81. <https://doi.org/10.17358/ijbe.9.1.81>
- Sandunima, K. C., & Jayasuriya, N. (2024). Impact of firm-created and user-generated social media marketing on customers' purchase intention in the fashionwear industry: Evidence from Sri Lanka. *South Asian Journal of Marketing*, 5(1), 61–73. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SAJM-04-2023-0029>
- Sanny, L., Arina, A., Maulidya, R., & Pertiwi, R. (2020). Purchase intention on Indonesia male's skin care by social media marketing effect towards brand image and brand trust. *Management Science Letters*, 10(10), 2139–2146. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.msll.2020.3.023>

- Sansern, C., Siripipatthanakul, S., & Phayaphrom, B. (2022). The relationship between digital marketing, customer relationship marketing (CRM), and online purchase intention: The case of Facebook live in Thailand. *International Conference On Research And Development (ICORAD)*, 1(2), 97–109. <https://doi.org/10.47841/icorad.v1i2.47>
- Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2010). *Research methods for business: A skill-building approach* (5th ed.). John Wiley & Sons.
- Sesar, V., Martinčević, I., & Hunjet, A. (2022). How influencer credibility and advertising disclosure affects purchase intention. *ENTRENOVA - ENTerprise REsearch InNOVation*, 8(1), 248–263. <https://doi.org/10.54820/entrenova-2022-0023>
- Setiari, D., & Ekawati, N. (2022). Peran iklan dan brand awareness terhadap niat beli pengguna tokopedia pada pasca Covid-19. *E-Jurnal Manajemen Universitas Udayana*, 11(8), 1550. <https://doi.org/10.24843/EJMUNUD.2022.v11.i08.p06>
- Shadi, E., Hesari, A., & Shahrabi, B. (2021). Relationship between social media marketing practices and customer response with mediating role of brand equity dimensions: An empirical investigation. *Independent Journal of Management & Production*, 12(5), 1583–1599. <https://doi.org/10.14807/ijmp.v12i5.1425>
- Shafaat, Z., Kishwa, F., & Alvi, A. (2020). The social media shaping brand consciousness and the purchase intention of fashion consumers. *Journal of Social Research Development*, 01(01), 30–45. <https://doi.org/10.53664/JSRD/01-01-2020-03-30-45>
- Shahneaz, M. A., Amin, M. B., & Eni, L. N. (2020). The Interplay between the psychological factors and entrepreneurial intention: An empirical investigation. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 7(12), 139–146. <https://doi.org/10.13106/jafeb.2020.vol7.no12.139>
- Shien, O., Huei, N. S., & Yan, N. L. (2023). The impact of social media marketing on young consumers' purchase intention in Malaysia: The mediating role of consumer engagement. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 13(1), 1540–1570. <https://doi.org/10.6007/IJARBS/v13-i1/15806>
- Shwastika, R., & Keni, K. (2021). The effect of brand awareness, social media marketing, perceived quality, hedonic motivation, and sales promotion towards consumers intention to purchase in fashion industry. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Economics, Business, Social, and Humanities (ICEBSH 2021)*. <https://doi.org/10.2991/as-sehr.k.210805.004>
- Singgalen, Y. A. (2024). Digital marketing of smartphone manufacturing product: Toxicity, social network, and sentiment classification. *International Journal on Social Science, Economics and Art*, 14(1), 73–86.
- Stone, M. (1974). Cross-validators choice and assessment of statistical predictions. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society Series B: Statistical Methodology*, 36(2), 111–133. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2517-6161.1974.tb00994.x>
- Turban, E., King, D., & Lang, J. (2009). *Introduction to electronic commerce*. Pearson Education, Inc.
- Vinzi, V. E., Chin, W. W., Henseler, J., & Wang, H. (2010). *Handbook of partial least squares* (Vol. 201, No. 0). Springer.
- Wijayaa, O., Sulistiyani, S., Pudjowati, J., Kartikawati, T., Kurniasih, N., & Purwanto, A. (2021). The role of social media marketing, entertainment, customization, trendiness, interaction and word-of-mouth on purchase intention: An empirical study from Indonesian smartphone consumers. *International Journal of Data and Network Science*, 5(3), 231–238. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.ijdns.2021.6.011>
- Yu, F., Wenhao, Q., & Jinghong, Z. (2022). Nexus between consumer's motivations and online purchase intentions of fashion products: A perspective of social media marketing. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 892135. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.892135>
- Zhang, W., Zhang, W., & Daim, T. U. (2023). Investigating consumer purchase intention in online social media marketing: A case study of Tiktok. *Technology in Society*, 74, 102289. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2023.102289>